

Missing Tile Syndrome: Robbing Ourselves of Happiness

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ABSTRACT

Life is a beautiful gift of God that we should always keep it in our mind. As a human being we always have a habit/tendency to focus on the things which we do not have in our life instead on focusing or realizing all positive things which are present in our own life, which is affecting our life quality. Ultimately it deprives many of the human being to achieve happiness in their life.

Key words: Missing tiles, ceiling, covetous

CONCEPT

It's so easy to focus on what we don't have in life rather than enjoying the things in our life that we do have.³ have u heard of "Missing Tile Syndrome"? This is something that we all tend to do. We generally emphasize *what is missing* instead of *what is present*, what is *negative* instead of what is *positive* in our life. Even though we have a life filled with happiness and all blessings, we often obsess for the things which are missing.

"Missing Tile Syndrome" is a term coined by Dennis Prager. It simply focusing on the things which we are missing and thus robbing ourselves of happiness. Imagine that you are in a Museum and looks up and see a beautiful ceiling made up with thousands of tiles. As u look around u notice that one of the tile is missing. Although the rest of the ceiling is perfect and beautiful but now you are not able to enjoy its full beauty just because of that one tile which is

missing. Upon that one missing tile, this has been called the "Missing Tile Syndrome".

It extends to all aspects of our life and how we relate with others. We all have a no. of desires but do not possess all many a times. Those are missing tiles in our life. We always try to achieve maximum and perfect in our life. There are some desire (missing tiles) which we cannot achieve (get replace/ fix). Although the missing tile in the ceiling can be fixed and looks the ceiling perfect and beautiful again. But unfortunately human beings have no limit for happiness and unfortunately there is not such 'Perfect life'.

Health will be in a big danger when we concentrate on our missing tiles continuously. We may experience various physical and psychological symptoms like unhappiness, anxiety, sadness, remorseful and ungrateful.

How to prevent Missing Tile Syndrome:-

1. Be grateful and thankful: we should always be grateful to God for the "tiles" having in our life and live a happy and better life. We may never have everything in life but we could always have something.
2. Fill yourself with the feeling of contentedness. It will ultimately make us satisfied with the things we have in life instead of missing things.
3. Do not be a grasping person. As in life we cannot have everything, but we must have something.
4. Do not be covetous. It is marked by inordinate desire for the same wealth as

another person. As a human being we always use to think about it. These types of feelings will make us to suffer with various kin of negative behaviour like stealing, robbery, murder etc.

Sign and Symptoms

- Feeling of sadness or despair
- Feeling of inferiority
- Feeling of hopelessness
- Feeling of dissatisfaction
- Feeling of helplessness

How to fix it?

1. Forget it sometime what is missing (If what you want is unrealistic)
2. Either work to get what's missing (If that's possible) or try to find modified way to get what you miss.
3. Try to find replacement or alternative (With an acceptable substitute). Sometimes we may be able to find even better.
4. Accept it or forget it. If the missing thing is not achievable try you best to forget it or not to think much about it. If u cannot change the thing at least accept it. It will at last give u satisfaction.
5. Replace your missing item with something else. For example. Being always focusing on inability to play cricket will only lead us in depression while go on to have a successful carrier in another filed makes us happy and healthy.
6. Decide with or without. You have to decide that u should always remains happy, no matter with or without that missing tile. You can 'achieve it', 'forget it', and 'replace it'.
7. If the missing tile is the centre for your happiness and it is the circle of your power then focus on how you might get or achieve it. For ex: finding a good match, changing job etc.

CONCLUSION

Most of what is missing in our lives, or what we think is missing, cannot be

replaced. Unlike a ceiling, life can never be made perfect. For that reason, concentrating on the missing tiles in your life is a big problem.

Most of what is missing in our lives, or what we perceived is missing, cannot be fixed. Unlike a ceiling, life can never be perfect always. For that reason, focusing on the missing tiles in life is a big problem, which is robbing our happiness. We all have one life to lead. Margus Aurellus once said: a man's life is what his thoughts make of it. Instead of worrying about what you can not control, shift your energy to what you can create. Be grateful for what you already have while pursue your goals. Remember, the only thing on which you can have a control is your own mental attitude. When your ceiling is mostly full of tiles take time to Live, Love and Laugh while you enjoy life.

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